

AESTHETIC ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING KNOWLEDGE OF SPORTS AESTHETICS IN FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical-methodological foundations of the development of knowledge about sports aesthetics in future physical education teachers, the practical methodical system of developing knowledge about sports aesthetics, and the effectiveness of developing knowledge about sports aesthetics have been studied. Motives for developing knowledge of sports aesthetics among future physical education teachers were also analyzed.

Key words: pedagogue, physical education, sports aesthetics, sport, technology, didactic, modernization, integration, cluster approach, fossilization education, reflexive, interactive, training, innovative, integrative.

INTRODUCTION. According to experts in the field of culture, beauty is the basis of culture. Maturity does not have the characteristics of flexibility or relativity. Perfection is absolute. Only ideality can be synonymous with perfection. The pursuit of perfection in sports is clearly expressed in the slogan "Citius, altius, fortius" (faster, higher, stronger) put forward by Baron Pierre de Coubertin. An athlete who strives for perfection can use all his strength to improve his result or surpass others in the competition. The highest result he can achieve is an ideal form. Ideal form can be manifested in everything in sports: a beautiful goal, a clear pass, a great shot, etc.; it can also be expressed in an almost imperceptible second of the game or in the game as a whole.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. The research of the pedagogical and psychological foundations of the development of the knowledge of sports aesthetics in future physical education teachers can be classified into three parts: studying in Uzbekistan, CIS countries and Western countries.

Uzbek scientists N.N. Tokhtaboyev, A.N. Shopulatov, S.S. Tajibayev, F. Kerimov, A. Shopulatov, A. Muzaffarov, A. Mirzayev, A. Khudoyorov work on the development of professional skills of physical education and sports specialists, formation of moral values in athletes. issues of effective organization are studied. Also, the scientific researches of S.Kh. Fayzulina, S.K. Annamuratova, A. Hasanov, F. Zorayev, A. Vosikhov, A. Sulaymonov, K. Dosimov have highlighted the educational possibilities of aesthetic education and sports aesthetics.

In Western countries, the issues of directing young people to the process of mass sports rehabilitation, rational use of the possibilities of sports aesthetics

and increasing the educational opportunities of physical education in this regard are discussed by scientists B. Lowe, H. Slyusher, F. Keenon, A. Vett, E. Researched by Zadarko, J. Junger, Z. Barabas, D. Brown, A. Alpers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. As the stage is for the actor, the ring, the field, the court are the same "stage" for the athlete. This is a boundary that no "game" can cross, and they are strictly regulated. If an athlete masterfully and uniquely performs all elements and wins many times in competitions of different levels, we have the right to say that he got his ability or talent from God, his parents, nature, and fate. One of the best gymnasts of all times and nations, L. Latinina, can be cited as a clear example of this.

An athlete must be able to feel balance, manage time, and control his mind and body in the process of intense movement. Any sport requires an athlete to have a sense of style and composition in rhythmic and continuous, creative and lively movement. In all types of sports, especially if the athlete has high skills, the accuracy of these actions, mutual proportionality, interdependence of movement styles are present in the form of compositional features for artists.

In recent decades, more and more attention has been paid to the "aesthetics of movement" in the field of sports. Despite the fact that the importance of aesthetic components in sports was paid attention to earlier, "sports aesthetics" as a specific direction began to be studied in the 70s of the 20th century. Looking at sports from the point of view of aesthetics, it is reasonable to assume that the athlete is an artist, and sports is a special form of art. So, how can you explain the diversity of sports beauty? Sport is perceived a little differently by an outsider and by the athlete himself. 3 therefore, how the participant of the competition perceives it, how he feels the strength of his skills, movements, agility, etc. k. - these constitute subjective perception with the help of senses. The perception and acceptance of his actions and aspirations by others is an objective perception and presentation. The difference between them is very serious, and at the same time, the probability that one person will feel and experience both of these feelings is very small. The ancient Greeks, who appreciated the value of art, named the benefits of physical exercises with terms such as "beauty", "elegance", "harmony". A number of sports are rich in elements of elegance, expressiveness of form, grace and perfection. Rhythmic gymnastics is one of the types of performing arts, the essence of which is revealed through dance-musical images, similar to ballet. Rhythmic gymnastics adds another dimension to the performance that involves creating illusions. We can say that illusion as a component of aesthetics is based on the ideas of Plato. A painter or

sculptor can create the illusion of movement. Also, complex elements used in rhythmic gymnastics or figure skating on ice create the impression that these movements are performed easily. But this is the result of daily hard work and hours of training. These performances give the viewer an aesthetic pleasure. It is the subtleties that distinguish a professional gymnast who is a real master of his profession, who shows his talent freely, from an athlete who has only technical training. A good gymnast's movements must be graceful, that is, he must be able to control himself and have a sense of rhythm (pace). When describing the actions of an athlete, we often use terms such as "aesthetics", "rhythm", "speed". They perfectly describe the elegance and beauty of sports. These terms are close to the concepts of "integrity" and "perfection".

For the ancient Greeks, the integrity of the composition was the first condition of beauty. It was important to achieve complete symmetry, i.e. proportion. Gradually, the law of integrity found its development in art. The unity (integrity) of space and time determined the unity of action. The principle of unity of body and soul, two forms of existence, formed the basis of the life of the Greeks, and we can assume that they did not look at athletic exercises as just a physical joke, a game. In Greece, sport was considered to be an activity that covers the human body as well as the soul. The participation of athletes is based on harmony (integrity, compatibility, proportionality of components). Everything must be compatible and in place; any exercise must be perfected. One of the relatively common aspirations in sports (one can say the main one) is to surpass others and one's own previous results and achievements, to show an even higher result. It can also be described as a superior result, an advantage that refers to an extremely high level of skill that an athlete has achieved or can achieve as a result of his pursuit of perfection. If this term is considered within the framework of culture, then we can see the striving for beauty. Despite the fact that long and short distance running are fundamentally different in terms of technique, each of them can be said to be attractive and beautiful in its own way. Each athlete has his own style - it is an individual (personal) characteristic that he demonstrates in one way or another. Both in sports and art, he is at the peak of perfection. The personality of the performer further enriches the technique he uses. Actions are an expression of his rich fantasy and imagination. Artistic activity consists of free expression of human fantasy and its mental (intellectual) capabilities. It can be concluded that the sportsman's control over space and time is lost due to the intensity and speed presented by the athlete during his

participation. Like art, sports provide an opportunity for self-expression, and beauty and entertainment provide public recognition and livelihood for sports.

Artistic representation of sports is found in the cultural heritage of many civilizations. Many artists and sculptors in different periods addressed the topic of sports. But the work of an artist or sculptor depends on his knowledge of sports. In addition, it is necessary to note the moment when the sports competition takes on the essence of actions that are unique to this type of sport. Some actions are performed so quickly, at lightning speed, that only an experienced eye can understand the essence of beauty in an unstable moment, stop a unique second, and "catch" a convenient mental moment. Often in sports news, cameramen present such movements of athletes that show not only the beauty of body lines, but also the unexpected aspiration that creates a centripetal force that occurs only in certain movements of the athlete.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, a photograph that captures the expressive, attractive movement of an athlete meets all the requirements of painting and sculpting art, as well as aesthetic requirements. A beautiful dribbling, performing complex gymnastic movements, moving gracefully and gracefully on the ice in a way that is memorable and beautiful, is truly an art. Thus, the feeling of satisfaction of the athlete from his favorite sport, the admiration of the audience for the perfect technique, the beauty of the athlete's body, and his constant desire to win in the game are reflected in real art. And these will later be reflected in cultural artifacts.

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